

Supplementary Material

Comparative immune response after vaccination with SOBERANA[®] 02 and SOBERANA[®] Plus heterologous scheme and natural infection in young children

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Supplementary Figure 1 Gating strategy B cell subpopulations analysis

Supplementary Figure 2: Distribution of B cell subpopulations in vaccinated and COVID-19-recovered children. PBMCs from vaccinated and COVID-19-recovered children (control) were isolated and stained with antibodies cocktails for B cell subpopulations. (A-F); Frequency of naïve B cells (CD19+IgD+CD27-) (a), exhausted B cells (CD19+IgD-CD27-) (b), pre-switched B cells (CD19+IgD+CD27+) (c), switched B cells (CD19+IgD-CD27+) (d), plasmablast switched B cells (CD19+ IgD-CD27+CD24-CD38+) (e), transitional naïve B cells (CD19+IgD+CD27-CD24+CD38+) (f) are shown for each individual as well as mean \pm SEM together with the p value from the Mann-Whitney non-parametric t test.

Supplementary Figure 3 Gating strategy IFN- γ secreting T memory cell subpopulations

Manual gating strategy for IFN- γ secreting T memory cell subpopulations after in vitro stimulation with S1 peptides.

Supplementary Figure 4 Gating strategy T helper subpopulations analysis

